

Supplementary Figures

The two faces of Janus: Why thyrotropin as a cardiovascular risk factor may be an ambiguous target.

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Supplementary Figure 1: PRISMA flow diagram of identified, screened and included studies

Supplementary Figure 2: Meta-regression of TSH, FT4 and FT3 concentrations with the interval between exposure to the stressor event triggering PTSD and the date of laboratory investigation of thyroid function.

Supplementary Figure 3: Forest plots showing differences in TSH, FT4 and FT3 concentration between subjects with and without PTSD in a subset of studies with chronic PTSD (24 months or more since the occurrence of the triggering event).

Supplementary Information

Supplementary Figure 4: Forest plots showing differences in TT4 and TT3 concentration between subjects with and without PTSD in all studies.

Supplementary Figure 5: Forest plots showing differences in TT4 and TT3 concentration between subjects with and without PTSD in a subset of studies with chronic PTSD.

Supplementary Figure 6: Funnel plots ruling out potential small-study bias in the meta-analysis.

Supplementary Figure 7: Directed acyclic graph (DAG) for the used model of instrumental variable (IV) regression. Confounders are variables that influence both allostatic load and thyroid function.